

ЯНГИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН МАЪНАВИЯТИ - ТАРАҚҚИЁТИМИЗ ПОЙДЕВОРИ**Ҳамдамова Манзура Зувайдиллаевна**

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Аннотация. Ушбу илмий мақола, сийсий ва амалий аҳамиятга эга бўлиб, мактабларда маънавий тарғибот ишларини олиб боровчи ҳар бир зиёли шахсларга мўлжалланган. Маънавият борасидаги янгича куч ва билимларни оила, маҳалла, умумий ўрта таълим мактабларида, маънавий-маърифий тадбирларни таъкил этишида миллий қадриятлар ва фазилатларни ривожлантириб, янгича билимларни амалга оширилишида кўмак беради.

Калит сўзлар: илмий, сиёсий, маънавий, маърифий, инсонпарварлик, миллий қадриятлар, тарғибот, янги куч, пойдевор.

НОВАЯ ДУХОВНОСТЬ УЗБЕКИСТАНА – ОСНОВА НАШЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ

Аннотация. Данная научная статья имеет политическое и практическое значение и предназначена для каждого интеллигента, ведущего духовно-пропагандистскую работу в школах. Она развивает новые силы и знания в области духовности в семье, районе, общеобразовательных школах, развивает национальные ценности и добродетели, помогает в реализации новых знаний.

Ключевые слова: научный, политический, духовный, образовательный, гуманитарный, национальные ценности, пропаганда, новая сила, фундамент.

NEW UZBEKISTAN SPIRITUALITY IS THE FOUNDATION OF OUR DEVELOPMENT

Annotation. This scientific article has political and practical significance and is intended for all intellectuals who carry out spiritual propaganda work in schools. It helps to develop new strength and knowledge about spirituality in the family, neighborhood, and secondary schools, in organizing spiritual and educational events, in developing national values and virtues, and in implementing new knowledge.

Key words: scientific, political, spiritual, educational, humanitarian, national values, propaganda, new force, foundation.

Entry. Today, New Uzbekistan, having set itself ambitious goals and objectives, is boldly taking steps towards achieving a standard of living among the developed countries of the world, building a just, free and prosperous society. Of course, we will not achieve this goal on our own. To do this, first of all, the state must have a solid and thorough program that will serve the near, medium and long-term prospects. Then, in order to fully implement this program, the entire people, every compatriot living on this land, all of us will need to work together and work effectively. The “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan” is just such a program.

In our country, special attention is being paid to fundamentally improving the system of working with youth, enhancing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work, elevating the intellectual capacity and mindset of young people, strengthening their ideological immunity, and raising them in the spirit of loyalty to the Homeland and respect for our national values.

The series of decrees and resolutions adopted by our state serve as an important programmatic document in this regard. During the expanded meeting of the Republican Council on Spirituality and Enlightenment held on December 22, 2023, under the chairmanship of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a number of tasks were outlined regarding the commissioning of centers for spirituality, enlightenment, and culture.

Sections on "National Crafts" established in all educational institutions are developing a new spiritual outlook among today's youth through workshops dedicated to traditional crafts that have evolved in our land over centuries: national gold embroidery, embroidery, ceramics, wood carving, miniature art, and other craft disciplines. Here, one can familiarize themselves with ancient art traditions, the rich experience of Uzbek artisans, examples of their creative work, and observe the secrets of ornaments and patterns used in craftsmanship. In many educational centers, the "Jadids Corner" displays exhibits featuring the instructive lives and constructive ideas of Jadid representatives such as Fitrat, Behbudiy, Cholpon, and Munavvar Qori, along with excerpts from their works. This section serves to acquaint youth with the Jadid legacy, draw lessons from the reforms of that era, and foster an educational spirit of knowledge and aspiration.

In recent years, as a result of the large-scale reforms and development work being implemented in our country, the consciousness, mindset, and worldview of our people have been transforming. The significance of the vital concept "From National Revival to National Advancement" in building a legal state and civil society is also growing. However, the economic, ideological, and conceptual contradictions occurring in the world today, alongside the intensifying pace of development and the impact of highly confrontational processes, are also being felt in our country. This necessitates a reassessment of the goals set based on the achieved results and accumulated experience.

At the meeting held on December 22, 2023, chaired by our President with the participation of cultural figures, representatives of literature and art, as well as leaders responsible for the effectiveness of work in this direction, key tasks in this sphere were defined following an analysis of the current state of science, education, enlightenment, and spirituality.

The reason is this: In states and societies developing towards high socio-economic progress, the proper organization of spiritual and educational processes is of critical importance. Especially in situations where threats to the Homeland and the destiny of the people intensify, it is precisely the nation's devoted intellectuals – vigilant-minded intellectuals, poets and writers, representatives of art, workers in the fields of spirituality and enlightenment – who courageously step forward. At this meeting, our state leader emphasized that at this current juncture, as our country enters a new, high stage of its development, we urgently need highly qualified personnel educated in the spirit of national values, just like our Jadid ancestors who were also nurtured on the achievements of Western science.

It must be acknowledged here that over the last seven years, a unified system has been created to increase the effectiveness and impact of spiritual and educational work, further expand its scope and scale, strengthen the sense of ownership among the country's population, primarily the youth, regarding the reforms being implemented, and coordinate work in the sector. The Law "On Cultural Activity and Cultural Organizations" was adopted. Centers for the Art of Maqom, Bakhshichilik, and Askia were established to preserve and enrich our national traditions. Furthermore, the activities of over 20 institutions were launched, including the "Bahor" Dance Ensemble, the State Philharmonic, and the State Symphony Orchestra; 11 new museums, 2 theaters, 28 children's music and art schools, and 5 higher education institutions were opened.

It was also announced at the meeting that a special Presidential Decree would be adopted for the development of the sector, a State Museum of Jadid Heritage would be opened at a historical site in Bukhara, and a foundation would be laid for a new newspaper named "Jadid".

This has now been implemented. All of this serves as a driving force for the people of Uzbekistan and forms the foundation of our new life.

Main Part. Spirituality is an organically interconnected system encompassing a person's ethics and manners, knowledge, abilities, practical skills, conscience, faith, beliefs, worldview, and ideological views, which exerts a positive influence on societal development. Indeed, a person's place in society is determined not by their material wealth, but by their high spiritual standing. From the very first years of our independence, issues of spirituality, youth upbringing, nurturing a well-rounded generation, and shaping a perfect individual were established as priority directions of state policy.

Because the future of any state, any society, its development, and its place in the world directly depends on the knowledge, competence, worldview, and spirituality of the country's youth. The decline of spirituality inevitably leads to a country lagging in development and falling under the influence of other states. It must be emphasized here that the essence and practical significance of spirituality become especially evident during turning points in societal development.

A series of resolutions aimed at further developing national spirituality have been adopted in our country, and consistent reforms are being implemented to create the new spiritual image of New Uzbekistan. These changes have elevated spiritual and educational work to an even higher position in our state policy. For example, we can cite Presidential Decree PQ-5039 dated March 26, 2021, "On the Establishment of a Fund to Support Spirituality and Creativity" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The decree outlines measures aimed at improving all spheres of spirituality.

In the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the fifth of the 7 main directions, "Ensuring Spiritual Development and Elevating the Sphere to a New Stage," comprises 8 goals, with spiritual education and upbringing designated as a separate priority direction. Large-scale reforms are being implemented in our country accordingly. Our ultimate goal is to build a democratic state governed by the rule of law and create a decent standard of living for our people. Achieving these goals is directly dependent on our people, especially our youth, and their moral and ethical upbringing. Nurturing youth in a spiritual and ethical spirit during the process of reforming our society, restoring our national values and true history, and possessing a national idea is an urgent task and occupies a central place in the complex of educational work. In recent years, developing the spiritual and ideological mindset of youth has been elevated to the level of state policy.

On December 22, 2023, an expanded meeting of the Republican Council for Spirituality and Enlightenment was held under the chairmanship of our state leader, Shavkat Mirziyoyev. During the meeting, our President emphasized the necessity of developing a separate program document that will serve as the methodological basis for the sphere of spirituality and culture, aimed at developing our national idea.

"History shows: In situations where threats to the Homeland and the destiny of the people intensify, it is precisely the nation's devoted intellectuals – vigilant-minded intellectuals, poets and writers, representatives of art, workers in the fields of spirituality and enlightenment – who have courageously stepped forward.

At this current juncture, as our country enters a new, high stage of its development, we urgently need highly qualified personnel educated in the spirit of national values, just like our Jadid ancestors who were also nurtured on the achievements of Western science," emphasized Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

Looking back at history, the great conqueror Amir Timur, as an unparalleled bright historical figure, viewed with great interest the scientific-philosophical teachings of his people, which nurtured him, provided him spiritual nourishment, and inspired him to great deeds. His deep awareness of the natural-scientific, socio-political, and philosophical teachings of great Eastern thinkers such as Al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina (Avicenna), and Abu Rayhan Beruni is no secret to anyone today. To understand the essence of Amir Timur's teachings on spirituality, enlightenment, religion, and ethics-morality more deeply and completely, it is sufficient to review the codes of ethics, counsels, and testaments he himself created, as well as the works written about him by other scholars. These include "The Code of Timur" (Temur Tuzuklari), "The Counsels of Amir Timur," "The Testament of Amir Timur," Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi's "Zafarnama," Ibn Arabshah's "History of Amir Timur," Salohiddin Toshkandiy's "Timurnoma," A. Akhmedov's "Lessons from History" and "Amir Timur," Evgeny Berezikov's "The Great Timur," Ashraf Akhmedov's works on the conqueror's biography, among others.

Considering Nelson Mandela's words, "Do not expect a nation that does not know how to discard trash into a trash bin to place the right person in the right position," it is essential, first and foremost, that every individual knows how to improve themselves and can serve as an example to the youth around them. Only when a person considers themselves a tiny part of the people, thinks about the people, and works for their benefit, do they become connected to spiritual morality. Raising youth within the family circle until they reach adulthood, nurturing them to be patriotic, cultured, and enlightened, is not only the duty of parents and teachers but also of their peers.

In ensuring that our country's youth become leading specialists in their fields in the future and make worthy contributions to societal development, reforms are also being implemented in several schools in the Tashkent region, primarily concerning their spiritual maturity and formation as well-rounded individuals. In this regard, a promotional project titled "The Foundation of Spiritual Reforms" was developed by professors, teachers, listeners, and methodologists of our center, and spiritual-educational events are being held in schools under this slogan.

The promotional project is carried out under the principle of "Peer to Peer," where student youth convey the content and essence of the large-scale reforms being implemented in our country, as well as the speech by our state leader Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the expanded meeting of the Republican Council for Spirituality and Enlightenment on December 22, 2023, to school students. In general, spirituality is considered the most important issue that everyone should engage with. This is not only the duty of deputy directors for spiritual-educational work but the high duty of every enlightened person. Therefore, the infusion of new light, new enlightenment into society must become the main task of every member of society. Ultimately, any state, any people is powerful by virtue of its intellectual competence and high spirituality.

Conclusion and Proposals. In shaping the political and legal culture of youth, we should, first and foremost, be able to instill in our student youth a sense of pride in the fact that they were born and live on this sacred land, and that they are the successors of world-renowned

great scholars like Al-Khwarizmi, Al-Farghani, Ismail al-Bukhari and Al-Termizi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Biruni, and Alisher Navoi. If we can awaken this feeling within youth, a sense of responsibility for comprehensively developing our state will manifest in their actions, consciousness, and thoughts.

In further elevating societal spirituality, nurturing independent thinkers with strong faith, firm convictions, who harmonize personal interests with national and public interests, and who are free and well-rounded individuals in all respects, must become the primary goal of every pedagogue. In today's globalizing world, preventing threats to information security has become one of the most urgent issues. At the same time, protecting our student youth from these information security threats demands strong attention and responsibility not only from parents but also from the education system personnel.

Observing the events unfolding around us, it is not difficult to perceive that spirituality and ethics are the primary factor as the Creator of all reality in the world. Of course, globalization processes are characterized by increased integration and cooperation between states and peoples, the emergence of conveniences for the free movement of capital, goods, and labor, the rapid dissemination of scientific achievements, the harmonization of various values on a universal human basis, and the acquisition of new quality in intercivilizational dialogue. That is, as our First President Islam Karimov aptly put it, "globalization means, first and foremost, an immeasurable acceleration of the pace of life."

As long as human society exists, opposing forces belonging to two poles will always collide. These are good and evil, virtue and vice, mercy and wrath, constructive and destructive forces. Spiritual decline, rootlessness (cosmopolitanism) and fundamentalism, militant racism, great-power chauvinism, extreme nationalism, fascism, and Bolshevism constitute precisely such a system of destructive ideas. As emphasized by First President Islam Karimov in his work "High Spirituality is an Invincible Force," issues of spirituality, youth upbringing, preventing ideological threats, and moral-ethical maturity have become very urgent problems. "Today, our youth receive diverse information and knowledge not only in educational institutions but also through radio-television, the press, the Internet, and other means. In such an environment, rapidly expanding in the global information space, raising our children one-sidedly by merely fencing off their consciousness, telling them 'don't read this, don't look at that,' isolating them with an iron wall undoubtedly does not meet the demands of the times nor our goals and aspirations. Why? Because we have set the firm goal of building an open and free democratic society in our country, and we will never deviate from this path."

In the current globalization context, the role and place of mass media (OAV) are of great importance in selectively delivering information to the public. In summary, at a time when ideological threats are exerting their influence to capture the consciousness and hearts of our student youth, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Protecting Children from Information Harmful to Their Health," initiated by President Sh. Mirziyoyev was adopted to strengthen cooperation among parents, the mahalla (neighborhood community), and pedagogues, and to prevent indifference. The purpose of this Law is defined as regulating relations in the field of protecting children from information harmful to their health.

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